

Exploring Strategies for Refining Column-and-Constraint Generation in Solving Two-Stage P2P Energy Trading Models under Uncertainty

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Abstract

This paper explores two strategies to enhance the column-and-constraint generation (CCG) algorithm for solving a two-stage stochastic peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading model under high scenario dimensionality. The first strategy introduces a delayed activation mechanism to control how frequently new scenarios are added to the master problem (MP), while the second initializes the algorithm with a representative subset of scenarios to enhance early-stage convergence. The model captures operational decisions of distributed energy resources under uncertainty, where efficient scenario management becomes crucial for tractability. The proposed strategies are evaluated through simulations on the IEEE 33-bus system, focusing on their impact on execution time, iteration count, and the number of scenarios ultimately activated in the MP. Results show that selecting an appropriate strategy involves a trade-off between computational time and problem size. Some configurations reduce execution time by up to 29% compared to the classic CCG approach, while others decrease the number of activated scenarios by over 20%, enabling the solution of larger-scale instances at the expense of moderately increased runtimes.

Keywords: Large-scale optimization; P2P energy trading; Column-and-Constraint; Optimization.

1. Introduction

The European Union (EU) has set ambitious energy objectives and policies to be achieved by 2030, collectively known as the "Clean Energy for All Europeans" initiative. Among these objectives is the commitment to reduce greenhouse gas emissions by at least 40% compared to 1990 levels [6]. Additionally, the EU aims to cover a minimum of 32% of its energy consumption with Renewable Energy Sources (RES), such as wind, solar, hydroelectric, and biomass [12]. Achieving these goals has spurred the development of innovative approaches to local energy organization and management. One such approach is the creation of Energy Communities (ECs), which aim to decentralize energy production and distribution, moving away from traditional centralized models [2]. A defining characteristic of ECs is Peer-to-Peer (P2P) energy trading, where energy is exchanged directly between participants within the community. In P2P energy trading, participants

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or agents typically fall into two categories: prosumers, who both produce and consume energy, and consumers, who only consume energy. These exchanges are primarily designed to maximize benefits for all participants within the EC and promote an efficient use of distributed energy resources (DERs) [34].

In this regard, for an EC to function effectively, the active participation of all its agents is crucial [26]. This requires participants to perceive tangible benefits aligned with their involvement in the EC. To achieve this, optimization methods are essential for ensuring efficient and equitable distribution of energy and benefits [8]. However, as ECs expand, both in the number of users and the assets they manage, the complexity of the optimization problem increases significantly, primarily due to the need to coordinate the operation of multiple assets across the distribution network (DN) [24]. This is further compounded by the uncertainty in energy supply and demand, particularly in the context of the day-ahead market. Addressing this growing complexity necessitates the development of more efficient algorithms, not only to reduce computation time but also to ensure feasibility within the constraints of available computational resources, especially memory [15].

Various decomposition techniques have been proposed to scale optimization in P2P energy markets within ECs [40]. Benders decomposition (BD) [17], for example, has been used to separate market and network decisions under uncertainty. However, the master problem (MP) can grow rapidly as the number of users with DERs increases, since each subproblem (SP) generates multiple Benders cuts, typically one per user per scenario, which are then aggregated into the MP. While useful for convergence, this multi-cut structure significantly increases the MP's size and computational burden. On the other hand, the Column-and-Constraint Generation (CCG) [13] algorithm offers a more scalable alternative by transferring only the most critical scenario-specific constraints from the SP to the MP. This selective inclusion is especially useful in EC operational models, where the structure requires incorporating second-stage variables, such as network flows, into the MP. Unlike classical decompositions, the MP in these models is not limited to first-stage decisions, so each added scenario increases its size. CCG thus offers a flexible framework for managing complexity, allowing selective activation of scenario- and user-specific constraints in the MP. This feature opens the door to exploring alternative strategies for determining which constraints should be incorporated at each iteration to balance convergence speed and computational efficiency.

This article proposes and evaluates exploratory strategies to refine the classical CCG algorithm when applied to a two-stage stochastic optimization (TSSO) problem for P2P energy trading in ECs. Rather than introducing modifications to the algorithm itself, the focus lies on investigating how alternative strategies for managing scenario activation can influence its scalability and computational performance. The main contributions of this work are threefold: i) a systematic exploration of scenario management strategies, applied individually or in combination, to assess their impact on convergence and problem size; ii) evidence of a potential reduction in the dimensional growth of the MP by delaying or limiting the inclusion of scenario-specific constraints; and iii) the demonstration that such strategies enable the solution of larger and more complex instances of P2P market models under uncertainty.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a review of the literature on

algorithms used to manage P2P energy trading in DNs. Section 3 introduces the extended TSSO formulation and its compact representation. Section 4 describes the methodology used to reduce the complexity of the TSSO model and outlines the implementation of the CCG algorithm on the resulting reduced formulation. Section 5 presents the proposed strategies for refining the CCG algorithm. Section 6 details the case study and discusses the computational results. Finally, Section 7 summarizes the main conclusions of the study.

2. Literature review

Among decomposition-based algorithms, BD has been widely applied to large-scale stochastic optimization problems, particularly those with a two-stage structure, where it separates first-stage decisions from second-stage recourse actions. In the context of ECs, various studies have employed BD-based approaches to address complexity and enhance scalability. For example, the work done in [27] proposes a multi-cut Benders framework for long-term planning of collective PV systems, efficiently handling degradation over time. The authors in [28] develop an enhanced BD method to coordinate microgrids with utility grids, preserving privacy while achieving decentralized optimality. The work in [38] introduces a hierarchical local market structure integrating P2P and community-based trading through multi-cut BD, and in [35] designs a privacy-preserving P2P trading model leveraging BD under renewable uncertainty. Despite these advances, BD often struggles with computational efficiency in large-scale settings, due to the rapid accumulation of cuts and the memory burden associated with managing them [7]. Moreover, its iterative nature can lead to slow convergence in problems with high uncertainty and dimensionality [3], motivating the adoption of alternative decomposition strategies better suited for modern ECs.

One such alternative is the Alternating Direction Method of Multipliers (ADMM) [18], which has recently gained traction as a promising approach for tackling large-scale stochastic optimization problems, particularly in the energy sector. Its primary advantage lies in its ability to decompose complex convex problems into smaller, independent subproblems that can be solved in parallel, making it especially attractive for distributed energy systems under uncertainty. In the context of P2P energy trading, ADMM has been widely adopted due to its flexibility, scalability, and privacy-preserving capabilities. For instance, [21] proposes a distributed pricing mechanism that considers battery degradation while preserving participant privacy. Similarly, the authors in [22] develop an ADMM-based algorithm for coordinated P2P electricity and carbon trading among multi-energy microgrids, enabling autonomous yet consistent decision-making across agents. The work done by [1] applies ADMM in a decentralized P2P market framework that respects distribution grid constraints and ensures privacy by limiting data exchange between peers. Additional studies highlight the method's versatility in energy applications: [29] address energy trading under uncertainty; [16] manage operational challenges under wind variability; and [20] examine its use in P2P markets with renewable generation uncertainty. While ADMM offers rapid convergence and ease of implementation, its inability to consistently guarantee global optimality in non-convex or highly coupled settings remains a limiting factor [32].

In recent years, the CCG algorithm has also emerged as a powerful alternative to traditional decomposition

methods for large-scale stochastic optimization, particularly when dealing with a high number of scenarios and intricate uncertainty structures. Structurally, CCG builds upon the BD framework, iteratively decomposing a two-stage problem into an MP and SPs per scenario, but with enhanced flexibility in scenario and constraint management. The work in [36] demonstrated the algorithm’s superior performance compared to classical Benders in two-stage robust location problems, reporting order-of-magnitude improvements in computational speed. This performance advantage has been further substantiated in [33], who showed that CCG outperforms both Benders and its multicut variants in memory usage and runtime when solving high-dimensional robust optimization problems. In energy systems, CCG has proven effective for complex decision-making tasks such as day-ahead unit commitment [31] and economic dispatch [9], where it efficiently manages large scenario sets while preserving solution accuracy. Recent studies also illustrate the algorithm’s adaptability to ECs. For example, [19] leverages CCG for multi-objective EC optimization, balancing trade-offs between cost and environmental impact. Similarly, the authors in [4] and [25] highlight its potential for managing renewable uncertainties and its promising synergy with learning-based techniques. These findings position CCG as a robust and scalable solution methodology for ECs under uncertainty, offering computational tractability without compromising optimality.

The decomposition algorithms discussed in the previous sections have demonstrated effectiveness in modeling the growing complexity of ECs, enabling the integration of multiple users, distributed assets, and uncertainties related to demand, generation, pricing, and privacy. However, P2P energy trading within ECs introduces a particularly demanding optimization context. These models must simultaneously capture the heterogeneity of users equipped with DERs, enforce network constraints, and evaluate performance over a large set of scenarios to realistically represent uncertainty in supply, demand, and pricing [20]. As the number of participants and assets increases, the dimensionality of the decision space expands rapidly, leading to computational challenges that can strain even the most advanced solution methods. Recent studies confirm that these scalability issues are particularly acute in P2P frameworks, where decentralized interactions and scenario proliferation significantly degrade algorithmic efficiency and solution quality [10]. These limitations raise important questions about the ability of classical decomposition techniques to adapt to the structural and computational requirements of P2P trading and motivate a critical assessment of their respective strengths and weaknesses in this context [23].

While methods such as the ADMM and BD have shown promise in decentralized optimization, each presents notable limitations in this context. ADMM excels at decomposing problems across agents and preserving privacy, but it struggles to accommodate network-level coupling constraints, often requiring simplifications or relaxed representations [16]. The authors in [39] also suggest that it may fail to deliver exact optimality in complex scenarios. BD, on the other hand, naturally retains such coupling and enables distributed computation, but suffers from poor scalability due to the exponential growth of Benders cuts and MP variables as the number of scenarios and users increases [7, 3]. These drawbacks motivate exploring alternative solution strategies that balance structural fidelity and computational tractability. One promising

candidate is the CCG algorithm [36], which is recognized for its reliability in producing precise solutions. The work done in [5] highlights that CCG leverages the decomposition logic of BD while avoiding the burden on the MP by activating only a subset of relevant constraints at each iteration. This selective activation makes CCG particularly well-suited to large-scale stochastic P2P models, where both scenario and user dimensions are high. Nevertheless, as highlighted by [36], [37], and [33], the conventional approach of incorporating the most violated scenario at each iteration can still cause the MP to grow rapidly. This opens the door to exploring alternative strategies for refining CCG. Specifically, approaches that control when and which constraints are activated during the iterative process.

In light of these challenges, this work investigates scalable strategies to refine applying the classical CCG algorithm to a TSSO model for P2P energy trading. Rather than modifying the algorithm itself, the focus lies on exploring alternative scenario activation rules to evaluate their impact on scalability with respect to the number of scenarios. The proposed strategies aim to limit the growth of the MP, improving tractability without compromising solution quality.

3. Two-Stage P2P energy trading model

This section presents how the original TSSO model for P2P energy trading in DN, proposed in [17], was reformulated to address its scalability limitations by applying the CCG algorithm. Thus, we consider a low-voltage DN represented by a directed graph $\mathcal{G} = (\mathcal{B}, \mathcal{L})$, where \mathcal{B} denotes the set of buses and \mathcal{L} the set of distribution lines, each connecting a pair of adjacent buses i and j . The users connected to the network are represented by a subset $\mathcal{A} \subseteq \mathcal{B}$, where each user can either be a prosumer, equipped with a PV system of capacity Γ_i^{pv} and a BESS of capacity Γ_i^{bt} , or a traditional consumer without local generation, both aiming to meet their electricity demand PL_i . At each time period $t \in \mathcal{T}$ and under scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$, a prosumer may experience an energy surplus, denoted as $\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+$, which can be injected into the LEM $p_{i,t,s}^{sm}$ or exported to the main grid $p_{i,t,s}^{sg}$. Conversely, in the case of an energy deficit $\Delta p_{i,t,s}^-$, the user may purchase energy from the LEM $p_{i,t,s}^{bm}$ or from the grid $p_{i,t,s}^{bg}$. The group of prosumers and consumers constitutes the EC within the DN. This community aims to minimize operational costs under a day-ahead market framework. In this context, the EC is required to commit, 24 hours in advance, to the hourly schedule of aggregated power purchases from the grid $p\kappa_t^{bg}$ and aggregated power injections into the grid $p\kappa_t^{sg}$, for all $t \in \mathcal{T}$.

Under the aforementioned market structure, the two-stage stochastic framework is particularly suitable, as it enables a clear separation between first-stage decisions, representing the energy commitments with the network operator, and second-stage decisions, corresponding to the operational variables that can be adjusted once uncertainty is revealed. Accordingly, the objective function defined in (1) seeks to minimize the total cost incurred by the EC, which comprises the cost associated with the aggregated energy purchased from the grid, as well as the expected operational costs arising from local generation.

$$\min_{p\kappa^{bg}, p\kappa^{sg}, pv} z = \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \left(\lambda_t^{bg} p\kappa_t^{bg} - \lambda_t^{sg} p\kappa_t^{sg} \right) + \sum_{t \in \mathcal{T}} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \rho_s (OC^{pv} pv_{i,t,s}) \quad (1)$$

The objective function in (1) minimizes the total operational cost of the EC. The first term corresponds to the first-stage decisions and represents, for each $t \in \mathcal{T}$, the net cost of the aggregated energy exchanged with the main grid, computed as the difference between the energy purchased at price λ_t^{bg} and the energy sold at price λ_t^{sg} . The second term captures the expected operational cost of local PV generation across all users $i \in \mathcal{A}$, time periods $t \in \mathcal{T}$, and generation scenarios $s \in \mathcal{S}$, weighted by the probability ρ_s of each scenario. The decision variable $pv_{i,t,s}$ denotes the power generated by the PV system of user i at time t under scenario s , and OC^{pv} denotes the corresponding unit operational cost. Thus, the feasible region of the optimization problem is defined by the set of operational decisions that comply with the physical constraints of the DN, the technical limitations of user-level resources, and the market rules governing energy exchanges.

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} p_{t,s}^{i,j} - \sum_{(j,i) \in \mathcal{L}} (p_{t,s}^{j,i} - R_{j,i} l_{t,s}^{j,i}) = \begin{cases} \Delta p_{i,t,s}, \\ p\kappa_t^{bg} - p\kappa_t^{sg}, \\ 0, \end{cases} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2a)$$

$$\sum_{(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}} q_{t,s}^{i,j} - \sum_{(j,i) \in \mathcal{L}} (q_{t,s}^{j,i} - X_{j,i} l_{t,s}^{j,i}) = qg_{i,t,s} - QL_{i,t,s} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2b)$$

$$v_{j,t,s} = v_{i,t,s} - 2(R_{i,j} p_{t,s}^{i,j} + X_{i,j} q_{t,s}^{i,j}) + (R_{i,j}^2 + X_{i,j}^2) l_{t,s}^{j,i} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2c)$$

$$(p_{t,s}^{i,j})^2 + (q_{t,s}^{i,j})^2 \leq l_{t,s}^{j,i} v_{i,t,s} \quad \forall (i,j) \in \mathcal{L}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2d)$$

$$p\kappa_t^{bg} \leq PG^{max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (2e)$$

$$p\kappa_t^{sg} \leq PG^{max} \quad \forall t \in \mathcal{T} \quad (2f)$$

$$QG^{min} \leq qg_{i,t,s} \leq QG^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{B}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (2g)$$

Eqs. (2a) through (2g) define the convex relaxation of the branch flow model [14], which captures the operational constraints of the DN in terms of line flows, voltage levels, and power exchange with the main grid. Specifically, Eq. (2a) enforces the active power balance, where the left-hand side represents the net active power flow into the bus, computed using the variables $p_{t,s}^{i,j}$ and the line losses $l_{t,s}^{j,i}$ scaled by the resistance $R_{j,i}$. The right-hand side of Eq. (2a) varies depending on the type of bus: for user buses $i \in \mathcal{A}$, it is given by the net power deviation $\Delta p_{i,t,s}$; for the interconnection point (substation), it corresponds to the net exchange with the grid, i.e., $p\kappa_t^{bg} - p\kappa_t^{sg}$; and for intermediate buses without generation or consumption, it is zero. Eq. (2b) imposes the reactive power balance at each bus, where $q_{t,s}^{i,j}$ denotes the reactive power flow on line (i,j) , $X_{j,i}$ the reactance, and $qg_{i,t,s}$ the reactive power injected at bus i , which is compared against the local reactive demand $QL_{i,t,s}$. Eq. (2c) models the voltage drop across each line $(i,j) \in \mathcal{L}$ using Ohm's law, where $v_{i,t,s}$ and $v_{j,t,s}$ represent the squared voltage magnitudes at the sending and receiving ends, respectively. Eq. (2d) defines the second-order cone relaxation that upper bounds the square of the apparent power flow by the product of the current magnitude squared $l_{t,s}^{j,i}$ and the sending-end voltage $v_{i,t,s}$. Eqs. (2e) and (2f) impose upper bounds on the aggregated active power bought from ($p\kappa_t^{bg}$) and sold to ($p\kappa_t^{sg}$) the main grid at each time period, constrained by the maximum substation capacity PG^{max} . Eq. (2g) defines the feasible range for

the reactive power injection $qg_{i,t,s}$ at each bus i , bounded between QG^{min} and QG^{max} , ensuring compliance with voltage support requirements and inverter capabilities.

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s} = pv_{i,t,s} - PL_{i,t,s} + ds_{i,t,s} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3a)$$

$$pv_{i,t,s} \leq \Gamma_i^{pv} PV_{i,t,s}^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3b)$$

$$soc_{i,t,s} = soc_{i,t-1,s} + ds_{i,t,s} \Delta t \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3c)$$

$$\Gamma_i^{bt} SOC^{min} \leq soc_{i,t,s} \leq \Gamma_i^{bt} SOC^{max} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3d)$$

$$-PB^{bt} \leq ds_{i,t,s} \leq PB^{bt} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (3e)$$

Eqs. (3a)–(3e) define the local energy balance and operational constraints for DERs at each user node $i \in \mathcal{A}$. Specifically, Eq. (3a) establishes the net power deviation $\Delta p_{i,t,s}$ as the result of PV generation $pv_{i,t,s}$, electricity demand $PL_{i,t,s}$, and battery operation $ds_{i,t,s}$. Eq. (3b) limits the PV generation to the available irradiance profile $PV_{i,t,s}^{max}$ scaled by the installed capacity Γ_i^{pv} . Battery dynamics are captured in Eq. (3c), where the state of charge $soc_{i,t,s}$ evolves based on the previous state and the charging/discharging action $ds_{i,t,s}$ over the time step Δt . Eq. (3d) constrains the state of charge between minimum and maximum thresholds, both scaled by the installed battery capacity Γ_i^{bt} . Finally, Eq. (3e) bounds the battery's instantaneous power exchange within $[-PB^{bt}, PB^{bt}]$, where positive values of $ds_{i,t,s}$ indicate charging and negative values represent discharging. This formulation assumes ideal (100%) round-trip efficiency and omits binary variables, which would otherwise be necessary to prevent simultaneous charging and discharging under non-ideal conditions.

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ = p_{i,t,s}^{sg} + p_{i,t,s}^{sm}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4a)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^- = p_{i,t,s}^{bg} + p_{i,t,s}^{bm}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4b)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+ = \mathcal{M} z_{i,t,s}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4c)$$

$$\Delta p_{i,t,s}^- = \mathcal{M} (1 - z_{i,t,s}), \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4d)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{sm} = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{bm}, \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4e)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{bg} = p \kappa_t^{bg} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4f)$$

$$\sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} p_{i,t,s}^{sg} = p \kappa_t^{sg} \quad \forall i \in \mathcal{A}, \forall t \in \mathcal{T}, \forall s \in \mathcal{S} \quad (4g)$$

Eqs. (4a)–(4g) define the constraints associated with P2P energy trading within the energy community. Eq. (4a) states that any energy surplus $\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+$ at user i can be allocated either to the main grid ($p_{i,t,s}^{sg}$) or to the LEM ($p_{i,t,s}^{sm}$), while Eq. (4b) specifies that an energy deficit $\Delta p_{i,t,s}^-$ must be covered by purchases from the grid ($p_{i,t,s}^{bg}$) or the LEM ($p_{i,t,s}^{bm}$). To prevent simultaneous buying and selling, Eqs. (4c) and (4d) introduce a binary variable $z_{i,t,s}$ and apply a big- \mathcal{M} formulation that forces $\Delta p_{i,t,s}^+$ or $\Delta p_{i,t,s}^-$ to be zero at each time and scenario, depending on the value of $z_{i,t,s}$. Eq. (4e) enforces market balance within the LEM by equating total

community-level energy sold and bought among users. Finally, Eqs. (4f) and (4g) define the aggregate power exchanged with the main grid in each period $t \in \mathcal{T}$, aligning the sum of individual purchases and injections with the first-stage variables $p\kappa_t^{bg}$ and $p\kappa_t^{sg}$, respectively.

To derive a compact TSSO formulation for the proposed P2P energy trading model, let $x = (p\kappa_t^{bg}, p\kappa_t^{sg})$ be the first-stage decision variables representing the aggregated day-ahead energy schedule with the main grid, and let $y = (pv_{i,t,s}, ds_{i,t,s}, soc_{i,t,s}, qg_{i,t,s}, v_{i,t,s}, p_{t,s}^{i,j}, q_{t,s}^{i,j}, l_{t,s}^{i,j}, p_{i,t,s}^{sm}, p_{i,t,s}^{bm}, p_{i,t,s}^{sg}, p_{i,t,s}^{bg}, z_{i,t,s})$ be the second-stage operational variables under uncertainty. Let $\xi = (PL_{i,t,s}, PV_{i,t,s}^{max})$ denote the uncertain parameters associated with load and PV availability, and define the expected scenario probabilities as ρ_s for all $s \in \mathcal{S}$. Thus, the constraints are partitioned into three disjoint subsets: (1) network constraints $\mathcal{H}_1(x, y, \xi)$, corresponding to Eqs. (2a)–(2g), (2) DER operational constraints $\mathcal{H}_2(y, \xi)$, corresponding to Eqs. (3a)–(3e), and (3) P2P market constraints $\mathcal{H}_3(y, x)$, given by Eqs. (4a)–(4g). Hence, the compact TSSO formulation is given by:

$$(TSSO) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \min_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \quad c_1^\top x + \mathbb{E}_\xi[Q(x, \xi)] \\ \text{where } \quad Q(x, \xi) = \min_y \quad c_2^\top y \\ \text{s.t.} \quad \mathcal{H}_1(x, y, \xi) = 0 \\ \quad \quad \mathcal{H}_2(y, \xi) = 0 \\ \quad \quad \mathcal{H}_3(x, y) = 0 \\ \quad \quad y \in \mathbb{Y} \end{array} \right. \quad \begin{array}{l} (5a) \\ (5b) \\ (5c) \end{array}$$

4. Column-and-constraint generation algorithm

While the compact TSSO formulation presented in (5) captures the operational and market dynamics of the energy community, the inclusion of binary variables in the P2P trading layer poses significant challenges for scalability, particularly when solving large instances with many scenarios or when incorporating dual-based decomposition techniques such as Benders cuts or CCG. We adopt a two-phase decomposition strategy to overcome this limitation, as illustrated in Figure 1.

In the first phase, we solve a reduced version of the TSSO model, which excludes the market constraints \mathcal{H}_3 , using the CCG algorithm. This step determines the users' optimal energy profiles under uncertainty, including the surplus or deficit at each node and time period. In the second phase, the results from the reduced problem are used to solve the P2P market-clearing problem, where trading decisions are optimized based on the power deviation $\Delta p_{i,t,s}$ obtained from the first phase. Note that the MP in this decomposition includes both \mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2 constraints. Unlike classical Benders decomposition, where the MP is limited to first-stage variables and the second-stage SP are solved independently, the CCG algorithm allows for partial inclusion of second-stage variables in the MP. Specifically, constraints in \mathcal{H}_1 , which represent the distribution network's power flow equations and operational limits, are always included in the MP. In contrast, the activation of constraints in \mathcal{H}_2 is scenario-dependent and evolves dynamically throughout the algorithm. As scenarios

Figure 1: Decomposition structure applied to the TSSO formulation for scaling the number of scenarios.

are added to the MP, the associated second-stage variables and constraints in \mathcal{H}_2 are activated in the MP and removed from the SP, effectively reducing the dimensionality of the latter. This structure enables a more efficient use of computational resources while preserving the network feasibility throughout the iterative process, as detailed in the following section.

The compact TSSO formulation in (5) is first reformulated to isolate scenario-dependent structures and address the scalability limitations posed by a large number of scenarios. Specifically, we express the second-stage variables and constraints with an explicit index $s \in \mathcal{S}$, enabling selective scenario activation during the iterative procedure. The reformulated version is shown in (6).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{x \in \mathcal{X}} \quad & c_1^\top x + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \rho_s Q_s(x) \\
 \text{where } \quad & Q_s(x) = \min_{y_s} c_2^\top y_s \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathcal{H}_1(x, y_s, \xi_s) = 0 \tag{6a} \\
 & \mathcal{H}_{2,s}(y_s, \xi_s) = 0 \tag{6b} \\
 & y_s \in \mathbb{Y}, \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}
 \end{aligned}$$

This scenario-indexed formulation enables a more explicit representation of the CCG decomposition into an MP and scenario-specific SPs. At each iteration, only a subset of representative scenarios $\mathcal{S}^0 \subseteq \mathcal{S}$ is activated in the MP, while the remaining scenarios $\mathcal{S}^1 = \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^0$ are used to evaluate the quality of the current solution and to generate Benders cuts. These cuts, derived from the dual SP solutions following [30], tighten the MP and ensure convergence. The decomposition is formalized in (7) and (8), where the MP aggregates the cost of active scenarios and approximates the cost of the remaining ones using auxiliary variables θ_s , while each SP independently solves for the recourse value of $Q_s(x)$, which in our case is further disaggregated at the user level as detailed below.

$$(MP) \left\{ \begin{array}{ll} \min_{x, y_s, \theta_{s,i}} & c_1^\top x + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^0} \rho_s c_2^\top y_s + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^1} \rho_s \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \theta_{s,i} \\ \text{s.t.} & \mathcal{H}_1(x, y_s, \xi_s) = 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^0 \\ & \mathcal{H}_{2,s}(y_s, \xi_s) = 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^0 \\ & y_s \in \mathbb{Y} \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^0 \\ & \theta_{s,i} \geq 0 \quad \forall s \in \mathcal{S}^1, \forall i \in \mathcal{A} \\ & x \in \mathcal{X} \end{array} \right. \quad (7)$$

Note that, in this work, we further refine the decomposition by observing that each scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$ can be independently disaggregated into user-specific SPs indexed by $i \in \mathcal{A}$. That is, the recourse function can be expressed as:

$$Q_s(x) = \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} Q_{s,i}(x),$$

where $Q_{s,i}(x)$ represents the individual subproblem associated with user i under scenario s . This user-level disaggregation enables a finer resolution of the second-stage problem and allows the generation of multiple Benders cuts per scenario—one for each user—thereby enhancing the approximation of unselected scenarios and potentially accelerating convergence.

$$(SP) \left\{ \begin{array}{l} Q_{s,i}(x) = \min_{y_{s,i}} c_{2,i}^\top y_{s,i} \\ \text{s.t.} \quad \mathcal{H}_{2,s,i}(y_{s,i}, \xi_{s,i}) = 0 \\ y_{s,i} \in \mathbb{Y}_i \end{array} \right. \quad (8)$$

The resolution of the decomposed model follows an iterative procedure that alternates between solving the MP and evaluating the recourse function $Q_s(x)$ via the SP for all $s \in \mathcal{S}^1$. At each iteration, the scenario sets \mathcal{S}^0 and \mathcal{S}^1 are updated, and Benders cuts are added to improve the approximation of inactive scenarios. The complete resolution procedure is summarized in Algorithm 1.

Algorithm 1: Column-and-Constraint Generation (CCG) algorithm

Initialize: $\mathcal{S}^0 \leftarrow$ initial scenario subset, $\mathcal{S}^1 \leftarrow \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^0$, $LB \leftarrow -\infty$, $UB \leftarrow +\infty$, $k \leftarrow 0$
1 while $\frac{UB-LB}{UB} > \delta$ **do**
2 $(x_k, y_k, \theta_{i,s,k}) \leftarrow$ Solve MP (7)
3 $LB \leftarrow c_1^\top x_k + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^0} \rho_s c_2^\top y_{s,k} + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}^1} \rho_s \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} \theta_{i,s,k}$
4 for $s \in \mathcal{S}^1$ **and** $i \in \mathcal{A}$ **do**
5 $Q_{s,i}(x_k) \leftarrow$ Solve SP (8)
6 if $Q_{s,i}(x_k) > \theta_{i,s,k} + \varepsilon$ **then**
7 $\left[\text{Move } s \text{ from } \mathcal{S}^1 \text{ to } \mathcal{S}^0 \right]$
8 $\left[\text{Remove } \theta_{i,s} \text{ and cuts for } (i, s) \text{ from MP} \right]$
9 $UB \leftarrow \min \{UB, c_1^\top x_k + \sum_{s \in \mathcal{S}} \rho_s \sum_{i \in \mathcal{A}} Q_{s,i}(x_k)\}$
10 Update incumbent: $(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) \leftarrow (x_k, y_k)$ if UB improves
11 Generate Benders cuts using duals of SP for all $(s, i) \in \mathcal{S}^1 \times \mathcal{A}$
12 Add Benders cuts to MP
13 $k \leftarrow k + 1$
14 return (\hat{x}, \hat{y}, UB)

Let the iteration index be $k = 0$, and initialize the incumbent solution as (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) . The MP includes only a subset of scenarios, denoted by $\mathcal{S}^0 \subset \mathcal{S}$, while the remaining scenarios form the complementary set $\mathcal{S}^1 = \mathcal{S} \setminus \mathcal{S}^0$. The lower bound is initialized as $LB = -\infty$ and the upper bound as $UB = +\infty$. In Step 2, at each iteration k , the MP defined in (7) is solved. It includes: the first-stage decision variables x ; second-stage variables y_s and the corresponding constraints \mathcal{H}_1 and $\mathcal{H}_{2,s}$ for all $s \in \mathcal{S}^0$; auxiliary variables $\theta_{i,s}$, which approximate $Q_{s,i}(x)$ for all $s \in \mathcal{S}^1$; and all previously generated Benders cuts. The solution is denoted by $(x_k, y_k, \theta_{i,s,k})$, and the LB is updated accordingly in Step 3. In Step 4, for each scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}$, $Q_{s,i}(x_k)$ is computed by solving the SP (8) for the user-level operational constraints $\mathcal{H}_{2,s}$. In step 6, we identify the scenario-user pair $(s^*, i^*) \in \mathcal{S}^1 \times \mathcal{A}$ that maximizes the violation $(s^*, i^*) = \arg \max_{(s,i) \in \mathcal{S}^1 \times \mathcal{A}} \{Q_{s,i}(x_k)\}$. If the violation exceeds a predefined tolerance, the scenario s^* is moved from \mathcal{S}^1 to \mathcal{S}^0 , thereby activating all associated user-level constraints in the MP during step 7. Remove the corresponding auxiliary variable θ_{i^*,s^*} and its associated Benders cuts (step 8). In step 9, the UB is updated, and in step 10, if the UB improves, update the incumbent solution as $(\hat{x}, \hat{y}) = (x_k, y_k)$. If the relative gap $(UB - LB)/UB \leq \delta$, for some predefined tolerance δ , the algorithm terminates, returning the incumbent solution (\hat{x}, \hat{y}) as δ -optimal. In step 10 for each scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}^1$, generate Benders optimality cuts $r_j^{s\top} x + \theta_s \geq v_j^s$, for $j = 1, \dots, k$, where the coefficients are derived from the dual variables π^s . These cuts are added to the MP in step 12, and the iteration counter is incremented: $k \leftarrow k + 1$.

5. Proposed Strategies for Refining CCG

The classical CCG algorithm explained above has proven effective for solving large-scale TSSO problems by iteratively incorporating scenario-specific constraints and dual-based optimality cuts. However, recent literature highlights that the efficiency of the CCG method is highly sensitive to how scenarios are selected and transferred from the SP set \mathcal{S}^1 to the MP set \mathcal{S}^0 . Traditionally, authors in [36], [37], and [33] recommend transferring the most violating scenario, i.e., the one maximizing $Q_{s,i}(x_k)$, in every iteration, immediately activating its associated constraints in the MP. While this strategy ensures fast responsiveness to SP violations, it may also cause the MP to grow rapidly, hindering scalability, particularly in complex power system applications such as P2P energy trading.

In this context, the structure of our model reveals a distinctive feature: unlike classical stochastic problems where only first-stage variables appear in the MP, our MP also includes a subset of second-stage variables and constraints, specifically those related to DER operation and network flow (\mathcal{H}_1 and \mathcal{H}_2). As a result, each scenario added to \mathcal{S}^0 significantly increases the size of the MP, motivating the need to explore alternative strategies to control this growth. Importantly, by keeping the user-level operational constraints \mathcal{H}_2 within the SP while maintaining the network-level constraints \mathcal{H}_1 in the MP, the subproblems can be decomposed not only by scenario but also by user. This enables the generation of multiple disaggregated Benders cuts per iteration (one for each user and scenario), enhancing the algorithm’s efficiency. In contrast, if \mathcal{H}_1 were handled entirely in the SP, such decomposition would not be possible, leading to weaker cuts and slower convergence. Accordingly, this work investigates two scenario management strategies to improve the trade-off between convergence speed and MP complexity. These strategies are inspired by insights from the above references, particularly the idea that strengthening the MP via Benders cuts alone, without prematurely increasing its dimensionality, can in some cases lead to more balanced performance. Thus, the proposed strategies, Iteration Strategy (IS) and Percentage Strategy (PS), are introduced and evaluated.

Iteration Strategy (IS): This strategy enforces a minimum number of iterations that a scenario must remain in the subproblem set \mathcal{S}^1 before it becomes eligible for transfer to the master set \mathcal{S}^0 . The purpose is to regulate the expansion of the MP by limiting the frequency with which new scenarios, and their associated constraints, are activated. In this study, the parameter $\alpha \in \{5, 10, 15\}$ determines the required number of iterations for each scenario, enabling an empirical assessment of how this delay impacts convergence and overall computational performance.

Percentage Strategy (PS): In this strategy, the algorithm is initialized with a predefined fraction β of the total scenarios directly included in \mathcal{S}^0 . While it is common to begin with an empty master set, initializing with a representative subset could offer useful structural information from the outset. The values $\beta \in \{10\%, 20\%, 30\%\}$ will be tested to evaluate whether this early enrichment can accelerate convergence or improve solution quality.

These strategies are designed to explore complementary aspects of scenario management: IS delays scenario activation to control MP growth, whereas PS injects initial information to guide early iterations. Both will be

evaluated individually and in combination to assess their potential to improve convergence behavior in the context of stochastic P2P energy trading problems.

It is worth noting that several alternative strategies could be explored for initializing the scenario set \mathcal{S}^0 . One natural option would be to preprocess the model’s input data to identify and include scenarios deemed most relevant to the solution. However, such a selection process is highly model-dependent and may introduce biases or limit generality. For this reason, we opt for a more generic and reproducible setup, focusing on strategies that do not rely on problem-specific heuristics. Moreover, the order in which scenarios are transferred from \mathcal{S}^1 to \mathcal{S}^0 is influenced by the initial composition of \mathcal{S}^0 . A fixed, deterministic selection may provide fast initial progress but can also lead to early convergence toward suboptimal paths, resembling behaviors observed in greedy algorithms. Figure 2 provides a visual summary of the strategies considered in this work, including the classical CCG and the two proposed variants. It also introduces a hybrid strategy (HS) that combines both ideas. From top to bottom, the diagram distinguishes strategies by their initial configuration: the top row starts with an empty master set ($\mathcal{S}^0 = \emptyset$), while the bottom row incorporates an initial percentage β of scenarios. From left to right, the diagram captures the timing of scenario transfers: the left-hand strategies admit new scenarios at every iteration, whereas those on the right impose a delay when the number of iterations \mathcal{I}^k is equal to α before permitting the inclusion of new scenarios.

6. Case Study

To observe the behavior of the CCG, the model solution will be applied to the IEEE 33-bus electrical network. This structure is commonly used for testing new algorithms and methodologies in power flow analysis, optimization, load flow studies, and fault analysis [11]. As shown in Figure 3, this network consists of 33 nodes and 32 branches connecting these buses. It is a radial distribution system, meaning it has a tree-like structure without any closed loops.

The same network and its associated requirements will be used for both the initial case with 20 distinct scenarios and the subsequent case with 50 scenarios. The primary difference lies in the increased number of possible scenarios for both solar production generation and user demand within the network. Given that our primary goal is to compare various strategies applied to the CCG, we prioritized enhancing computational efficiency to increase the number of models tested. While studies in this field typically involve simulating multiple agents across various scenarios, most practical applications commonly use between 3 and 10 agents due to computational constraints. For this study, we selected three agents to enable a broader exploration of different tests and strategies. The experiments were conducted on a computer with an Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-1235U 12th Gen processor runs at 1.30 GHz and has 16 GB of RAM, using the Pyomo library in Python. This means that the observed times are only comparative between the models and should never be considered immutable.

Figure 2: Summary of CCG strategy variants using scenario-user selection and scenario management

6.1. Computational Results

Both strategies (IS) and (PS) are applied individually and in combination to assess their interaction and identify which approach offers better performance. This evaluation aims to provide insight into the algorithm's behavior and its adaptability to different scenario configurations. Simulations are conducted using a reduced TSSO model to validate the proposed strategies, with an initial focus on the 20-scenario setup. This relatively small scenario set allows for a detailed examination of how each strategy affects convergence and scalability. Based on the results from this first phase, a decision is made regarding which strategy is most suitable for scaling up to a larger model with 50 scenarios. The second phase provides a deeper assessment of the CCG algorithm's scalability and performance under increased scenario complexity. Ultimately, the insights gained from both phases guide recommendations for refining the algorithm. For the strategies involving a nonzero initial activation of scenarios in the MP (i.e., $\beta > 0$), the active scenarios are randomly

Figure 3: IEEE 33-bus electrical network

selected at the beginning of the first iteration. To ensure robustness of the results under this randomness, each of these configurations is simulated 10 times, and the reported values in the tables correspond to the average performance across those runs. The variability introduced by this initial random selection is discussed separately at the end of this section.

It is important to note that this study adopts an exploratory approach, focusing specifically on the impact of scenario growth. To isolate this dimension, the number of users and DERs is held constant across all experiments. This assumption enables a focused analysis of how different scenario activation strategies affect algorithmic performance, measured in terms of (i) the number of iterations required to reach convergence, (ii) the total execution time, and (iii) the number of scenarios transferred to the MP. The objective is to identify promising directions for future refinements of the CCG algorithm in settings where the primary challenge lies in managing a large number of scenarios.

6.2. Results for 20 Scenarios

Table 1 presents the performance of all tested CCG strategies under a reduced test model with $|\mathcal{S}| = 20$ scenarios. The strategies are grouped into three categories: Percentage Strategy (PS), Iteration Strategy (IS), and Hybrid Strategy (HS), and are sorted in ascending order of total computational time. Four performance metrics are evaluated: total number of iterations to convergence, total solution time (in seconds), the percentage of scenarios left in the SP, and the cumulative solution time spent within the MP.

The first observation is that all PS configurations, defined by a preassigned activation of a fraction $\beta\%$ of scenarios in the initial MP (\mathcal{S}^0), consistently outperform the baseline classical CCG model in terms of both iteration count and execution time. Specifically, increasing β from 10% to 30% reduces the number of required iterations from 19 to 15 and the solution time from 906s to 498s, respectively. These results suggest that initializing the MP with a modest proportion of representative scenarios can significantly accelerate convergence. Moreover, the PS models concentrate most of their computational burden in the MP resolution phase, highlighting that early scenario activation leads to faster SP-MP feedback and quicker stabilization of dual information. However, despite their computational advantages, PS strategies uniformly converge only after transferring all scenarios into the MP ($\mathcal{S}^0 = \mathcal{S}$, i.e., 0% remaining in \mathcal{S}^1). While acceptable for small-scale settings, this behavior may compromise scalability in problems with hundreds of scenarios, where

Model	20 Scenarios			
	Iterations	Time [s]	Percentage	MP [s]
$PS_{\beta=30}$	15	498	0%	422
$PS_{\beta=20}$	17	620	0%	525
$PS_{\beta=10}$	19	906	0%	761
Classic	21	1163	0%	1104
$HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=30}$	48	1458	20%	1242
$HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=20}$	51	1640	29%	1386
$HS_{\alpha=10,\beta=30}$	58	1851	32%	1602
$HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=10}$	79	2352	38%	1988
$HS_{\alpha=15,\beta=30}$	77	2386	41%	2385
$HS_{\alpha=10,\beta=20}$	86	2765	42%	2319
$HS_{\alpha=15,\beta=20}$	98	3303	41%	2918
$IS_{\alpha=5}$	102	3444	30%	3271
$HS_{\alpha=10,\beta=10}$	103	3598	30%	3091
$HS_{\alpha=15,\beta=10}$	110	5294	42%	4326
$IS_{\alpha=10}$	115	6534	45%	6204
$IS_{\alpha=15}$	120	8034	55%	7632

Table 1: Strategies’ performance for 20 scenarios. The percentage column indicates the scenarios left in the SP when the algorithm converges.

fully populating the MP becomes impractical. In such cases, the algorithm effectively devolves into solving the deterministic equivalent, nullifying the intended decomposition benefits.

At the opposite end of the table, IS strategies adopt a stricter policy: a scenario $s \in \mathcal{S}^1$ is only promoted to the MP after it violates the current solution for α consecutive iterations. This approach dramatically limits the number of active scenarios needed for convergence. For instance, the $IS_{\alpha=15}$ model converges after activating only 45% of the scenarios. However, the cost of this selectivity is clear: IS strategies exhibit the longest solution times (up to 8034s) and the highest number of iterations (up to 120), owing to the delayed incorporation of violating scenarios and the increased number of MP reformulations required to restore feasibility and optimality. HS strategies lie between PS and IS in terms of performance. These models combine a fixed initial activation of scenarios (β) with delayed transfers governed by a violation persistence parameter (α). As expected, HS configurations provide a tunable trade-off between early convergence and reduced scenario inclusion. For example, $HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=30}$ achieves convergence in 48 iterations and 1458s, while activating only 80% of the scenarios. Increasing α or decreasing β generally leads to lower scenario activation but at the expense of higher iteration counts and computational times. This flexibility makes HS a compelling option when memory limitations or MP complexity are critical constraints.

In summary, Table 1 illustrates that although the PS approach achieves the fastest convergence for small instances, its aggressive scenario inclusion policy raises scalability concerns. IS strategies, on the other hand, prioritize MP compactness but at the expense of longer runtimes. HS strategies offer a configurable balance between these extremes. The analysis confirms the importance of scenario management policies not only for accelerating convergence but also for controlling MP growth, a crucial aspect when addressing large-scale stochastic problems in energy systems.

6.3. Strategy selection

Drawing from the analysis presented in the previous section, the strategy selected for the subsequent experiment, scaling the problem to $|\mathcal{S}| = 50$ scenarios, is the HS configuration with $\alpha = 5$. This variant offers a favorable trade-off: it achieves convergence without requiring the activation of all scenarios in the MP, while maintaining computational times significantly lower than those of the IS. Although it is marginally slower than the classical CCG and PS models, its ability to preserve a reduced scenario set in \mathcal{S}^0 makes it particularly suitable for large-scale applications, where fully populating the MP is computationally prohibitive.

Regarding the initial scenario activation parameter β , it was observed that its impact is less predictable due to its dependence on the specific composition of the initially selected scenarios. As a result, the upcoming analysis includes multiple values of β to further assess its influence on convergence behavior and computational efficiency. While HS configurations with $\alpha = 10$ could also be considered for their lower scenario inclusion rates, they exhibit greater performance variability and sensitivity to scenario selection. Therefore, HS models with $\alpha = 5$ are prioritized for their consistency and balance across the evaluated performance metrics. It is worth noting that, under even more demanding scenario dimensions, strategies with larger α values may become viable alternatives, particularly in cases where minimizing memory usage outweighs runtime considerations. However, this would likely require improved mechanisms for identifying which scenarios to activate, motivating future work on adaptive or learning-based activation rules.

6.4. Results for 50 Scenarios

Table 2 presents the performance results for the selected strategies when scaling the reduced TSSO model to 50 scenarios. As before, the models are sorted by total computational time. Three main trends emerge when analyzing the performance in terms of iterations, time, and the percentage of scenarios included in the MP, now under a higher dimensional setting.

Model	50 Scenarios			
	Iterations	Time [s]	Percentage	MP [s]
$PS_{\beta=10}$	28	2194	15%	2084
$PS_{\beta=20}$	30	2362	20%	2243
$PS_{\beta=30}$	34	2980	21%	2830
Classic	40	3093	21%	2939
$HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=20}$	87	5491	43%	4697
$HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=30}$	79	5678	35%	4862
$HS_{\alpha=5,\beta=10}$	92	6579	51%	5489
$IS_{\alpha=5}$	102	8373	58%	7105
$IS_{\alpha=15}$	110	11724	79%	11153
$IS_{\alpha=10}$	123	12920	75%	12292

Table 2: Strategies' performance for 50 scenarios.

First, the PS strategies remain the fastest overall, with execution times ranging from 2194 s to 2980 s, and requiring the fewest iterations. Notably, unlike in the 20-scenario case, where PS models required full scenario activation for convergence, here, these strategies achieve optimality using 85%–79% of scenarios. This suggests

that increasing the initial scenario pool ($\beta > 0$) can still offer convergence benefits without necessarily leading to full MP expansion, especially when the scenario space grows. The classical CCG model also converges with 79% of scenarios, although requiring more iterations and longer total time than the best PS strategies.

In contrast, the IS strategies ($\alpha \in \{5, 10, 15\}$) remain the most computationally expensive. These models take more than twice as long as the PS counterparts, with total execution times ranging from 8373 s to 12,920 s. Despite this, they activate significantly fewer scenarios, using only 42% to 25% of the total, highlighting their potential for reducing the dimensionality of the MP at the expense of additional iterations and delayed convergence. This behavior is consistent with the findings from the 20-scenario experiment and suggests that, under tight memory constraints, such trade-offs might be favorable for highly granular models. Hybrid strategies (HS), which combine both initial scenario activation and delayed transfer rules, continue to exhibit an intermediate behavior. The configuration $HS_{\alpha=5, \beta=20}$ stands out as a particularly balanced option: it converges using only 57% of the scenarios while requiring 87 iterations and 5491 s of execution time—offering a compromise between scenario economy and computational efficiency. Other HS variants demonstrate greater variability depending on β , confirming that the initial selection of active scenarios has a non-negligible impact on performance.

Figure 4: CCG Results for 20 and 50 scenarios.

These findings are summarized in Figure 4, where the three performance indicators, iterations (blue), execution time (red), and unused scenarios (green), are normalized to a radar chart. As in the 20-scenario case, the time and iteration metrics follow closely related patterns, with the PS and classical strategies clustering near optimal regions for these criteria. However, the green lines reveal an inverse behavior: strategies that are optimal in time and iterations tend to activate most scenarios, while those that minimize MP growth (notably IS and some HS configurations) perform worse in time. This reinforces the trade-off between execution time and MP scalability.

These results highlight two key insights with important implications for refining the CCG algorithm. First, the Percentage Strategy (PS) demonstrates that initializing the MP with a randomly selected subset of scenarios ($\beta > 0$) can significantly accelerate convergence without requiring full scenario activation—even

when the total number of scenarios increases. In the 50-scenario case, for instance, the PS models achieve convergence, leaving 15%–21% of the scenarios without activation in the MP while outperforming other strategies in both iterations and computational time. This suggests that there is latent potential in improving initial scenario selection heuristics. Rather than relying solely on random selection, future strategies could exploit structure or historical performance metrics to guide which scenarios should be activated at initialization. Such a refinement could preserve the PS strategy’s computational advantages while further reducing the number of unnecessary scenarios loaded into the MP.

Second, the Iteration Strategy (IS) and selected Hybrid Strategy (HS) configurations illustrate a different trade-off: by delaying the inclusion of scenarios into the MP (e.g., only after $\alpha = 5, 10, 15$ iterations), these models manage to significantly reduce the number of active constraints, in some cases using less than half of the scenarios. For example, $IS_{\alpha=15}$ converges using only 21% of the scenarios, offering a drastically smaller MP footprint compared to PS and Classical approaches. While this comes at the cost of increased runtime and iterations, the reduced dimensionality of the MP may prove advantageous in contexts where RAM usage or solver capacity is a limiting factor, such as when scaling up to hundreds of users, assets, or scenarios.

Together, these findings suggest that no single strategy dominates across all criteria, but rather that different strategies may be better suited to different deployment settings. PS-based approaches are ideal when rapid convergence is needed and memory is not a constraint. Conversely, IS- or HS-based strategies may be preferable in memory-bound applications where scenario pruning is essential. Crucially, the results underscore that controlling when and which scenarios are activated in the MP is a powerful lever for tuning the CCG’s scalability. This opens an avenue for further algorithmic development focused on adaptive or learning-based scenario activation policies tailored to the problem structure and resource availability.

6.5. Variability

This section analyzes the sensitivity of computational performance to the selection of initial scenarios in strategies involving $\beta > 0$. As described earlier, these strategies begin with a non-empty initial set \mathcal{S}^0 , populated by randomly selected scenarios. To capture the variability introduced by this randomness, each strategy was simulated 10 times using different initializations. Figure 5 presents the resulting dispersion in total solution time, providing insight into how initial scenario selection can influence convergence behavior under each configuration.

Figure 5 displays four distinct groups corresponding to each strategy involving a nonzero value of β . Within each group, the configuration with $\beta = 10$ consistently shows the highest variability in computational time. As β increases, this variability tends to diminish. This trend can be attributed to the relative influence of the initial scenarios: when only a few scenarios are activated in \mathcal{S}^0 , their specific characteristics heavily influence early iterations, making the initialization more sensitive. In contrast, higher values of β provide a broader representation of the uncertainty space from the outset, thereby reducing the impact of any individual scenario on the overall convergence behavior.

Figure 5: Variability of Time for 20 scenarios

For the HS strategy, three distinct subgroups can be identified in Figure 5, approximately forming a diagonal progression. Within each subgroup, an increase in the value of α is consistently associated with greater variability in computational time. This suggests that lower values of α are preferable when aiming to reduce sensitivity to the initial scenario selection. The underlying rationale mirrors that of the β trend: when α is large, newly identified violating scenarios are incorporated into the MP less frequently. If the initial scenario selection is suboptimal, this delayed incorporation can result in more iterations with incomplete or unrepresentative information in the MP, thereby amplifying variability and total execution time. Likewise, a notable disparity in variability is observed between the best-performing configuration, $HS_{\alpha=5, \beta=30}$, and the worst in terms of sensitivity to initial conditions, $HS_{\alpha=15, \beta=30}$. In the latter case, the combined effect of a high α and a moderate β , leads to significant performance fluctuations. Among the 10 simulations conducted for this strategy, computational times vary by over 2000 seconds, with some instances exceeding 6000 seconds while others remain below 4000. Remarkably, this internal variability within a single strategy surpasses the total execution time required by the classical CCG approach to solve the same problem instance.

These results underscore the significant influence that the initial selection of scenarios can have on the computational performance of the CCG algorithm. While an optimal choice of initial scenarios may substantially improve outcomes, it is also problem-dependent and introduces an additional layer of complexity. For this reason, the present study does not explore optimization strategies for scenario selection. Instead, the focus remains on evaluating the effect of different activation rules and their interaction with stochastic dimensionality. Nevertheless, developing systematic or data-driven methods for identifying effective initial scenario sets represents a promising direction for future research.

6.6. Further Work

As demonstrated in this paper, a foundation has been established regarding the strategies that can be applied to the CCG algorithm to improve its applicability to large-scale optimization problems. However, there is always room for algorithmic improvements. While the proposed strategies successfully reduce computational time and the dimensions of the MP, they remain quite rigid. A promising direction for future work could involve developing more flexible strategies. For instance, scenarios could initially be sent to the MP at each iteration, but as the MP grows larger, progressively more iterations may be required before new scenarios are added. Additionally, this work has highlighted the sensitivity of the initial scenario selection. Future studies could explore the impact of different strategies for selecting initial scenarios and analyze whether these strategies are inherently linked to specific types of problems. This could lead to more tailored and efficient approaches for particular optimization contexts.

7. Conclusions

This paper proposed and evaluated two strategies to refine the classical CCG algorithm for solving two-stage stochastic P2P energy trading models under uncertainty. The results show that managing scenario activation effectively can significantly improve both the scalability and computational efficiency of the CCG method.

The first strategy, based on delaying scenario activation through a frequency parameter (α), proved effective in limiting the growth of the MP, reducing the number of activated scenarios by up to 55%. Although this approach increases the number of iterations and total runtime, it enables solving larger instances that would otherwise be computationally intractable. The second strategy, which initializes the MP with a subset (β) of scenarios, accelerated convergence by providing structural information from the outset. This method consistently reduced execution times compared to the classical CCG, particularly when the initial scenario selection was representative of the overall uncertainty. Furthermore, the combination of both strategies into an HS achieved a favorable balance between runtime and MP size. Hybrid configurations enabled solving larger problems with a moderate increase in iterations while significantly limiting the master problem's dimensionality.

Finally, the study highlights the sensitivity of computational performance to the initial scenario selection, particularly in configurations with low β and high α . These observations underline the importance of future research focused on adaptive or data-driven strategies for scenario activation, aiming to further enhance the scalability of CCG in complex stochastic models.

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References

- [1] Aminlou, A., Mohammadi-Ivatloo, B., Zare, K., Razzaghi, R., & Anvari-Moghaddam, A. (2024). Activating demand side flexibility market in a fully decentralized p2p transactive energy trading framework using admm algorithm. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, *100*, 105021. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2210670723006327>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2023.105021>.
- [2] Barabino, E., Fioriti, D., Guerrazzi, E., Mariuzzo, I., Poli, D., Raugi, M., Razaeei, E., Schito, E., & Thomopoulos, D. (2023). Energy communities: A review on trends, energy system modelling, business models, and optimisation objectives. *Sustainable Energy, Grids and Networks*, *36*, 101187.
- [3] Bertsimas, D., Cory-Wright, R., Pauphilet, J., & Petridis, P. (2023). A stochastic benders decomposition scheme for large-scale stochastic network design. *Optimization Online*, . URL: <https://optimization-online.org/2023/05/9530/>.
- [4] Chen, L., Zhang, H., & Wang, Y. (2023). Optimizing energy resource allocation using column and constraint generation under uncertainty. *Energy Reports*, *9*, 789–803.
- [5] Cheng, R., Wang, H., & Sun, X. (2024). Exact optimization in high-dimensional energy systems using column and constraint generation. *Energy Systems Research*, *39*, 73–85.
- [6] Comisión Europea (2016). La Comisión Europea - Comunicado de prensa: Comunicación sobre una nueva agenda europea para la economía colaborativa. URL: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/es/IP_16_4009 accessed: 2024-04-29.
- [7] Cordeau, J.-F., Furini, F., & Ljubić, I. (2019). Benders decomposition for very large scale partial set covering and maximal covering location problems. *European Journal of Operational Research*, *275*, 882–896.
- [8] Cornélusse, B., Savelli, I., Paoletti, S., Giannitrapani, A., & Vicino, A. (2019). A community microgrid architecture with an internal local market. *Applied Energy*, *242*, 547–560.
- [9] Ding, T., & Zhao, C. (2016). Robust optimal transmission switching with the consideration of corrective actions for n-k contingencies. *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, *10*, 3288–3295.
- [10] Doan, H. T., Nam, H., & Kim, D. (2023). Optimal peer-to-peer energy trading under load uncertainty incorporating carbon emission and transaction cost for grid-connected prosumers. *Energy Reports*, *9*, 1440–1456.

- [11] Dolatabadi, S. H. et al. (2020). An enhanced iee 33 bus benchmark test system for distribution system studies. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, *36*, 2565–2572.
- [12] European Parliament (2024). Renewable energy. URL: <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/factsheets/en/sheet/70/renewable-energy> accessed: 2024-08-21.
- [13] Fanzeres, B., Street, A., & Pozo, D. (2020). A column-and-constraint generation algorithm to find nash equilibrium in pool-based electricity markets. *Electric power systems research*, *189*, 106806.
- [14] Farivar, M., & Low, S. H. (2013). Branch flow model: Relaxations and convexification—part i. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, *28*, 2554–2564. doi:[10.1109/TPWRS.2013.2255317](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRS.2013.2255317).
- [15] Gamarra, C., & Guerrero, J. M. (2015). Computational optimization techniques applied to microgrids planning: A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, *48*, 413–424. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1364032115002956>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2015.04.025>.
- [16] Gao, H., Wang, J., Liu, Y., Wang, L., & Liu, J. (2020). An improved admm-based distributed optimal operation model of ac/dc hybrid distribution network considering wind power uncertainties. *IEEE Systems Journal*, *15*, 2201–2211.
- [17] García-Muñoz, F., Dávila, S., & Quezada, F. (2023). A benders decomposition approach for solving a two-stage local energy market problem under uncertainty. *Applied Energy*, *329*, 120226.
- [18] Glowinski, R., & Marroco, A. (1975). Sur l’approximation, par éléments finis d’ordre un, et la résolution, par pénalisation-dualité d’une classe de problèmes de dirichlet non linéaires. *Revue Française d’Automatique, Informatique, Recherche Opérationnelle. Analyse Numérique*, *9*, 41–76.
- [19] Gonzalez, A. et al. (2022). Multi-objective optimization in energy communities: A ccg approach. *Energy Reports*, *8*, 173–183. doi:[10.1016/j.egyr.2021.11.030](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.egyr.2021.11.030).
- [20] Guo, Z., Pinson, P., Chen, S., Yang, Q., & Yang, Z. (2020). Chance-constrained peer-to-peer joint energy and reserve market considering renewable generation uncertainty. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, *12*, 798–809.
- [21] Han, B., Zahraoui, Y., Mubin, M., Mekhilef, S., Korõtko, T., & Alshammari, O. (2024). Distributed optimal storage strategy in the admm-based peer-to-peer energy trading considering degradation cost. *Journal of Energy Storage*, *96*, 112651. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352152X24022370>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.est.2024.112651>.
- [22] Hou, H., Wang, Z., Zhao, B., Zhang, L., Shi, Y., Xie, C., Dong, Z., & Yu, K. (2024). Distributed optimization for joint peer-to-peer electricity and carbon trading among multi-energy microgrids considering renewable generation uncertainty. *Energy*

- Conversion and Economics*, 5, 116–131. URL: <https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1049/enc2.12110>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1049/enc2.12110>. arXiv:<https://ietresearch.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1049/enc2.12110>.
- [23] Khan, M. A., Rehman, A., & Khan, M. A. (2023). A review on optimal energy management techniques for energy trading: Current trends and future directions. *Energies*, 16, 2069.
- [24] Li, Y., Han, M., Yang, Z., & Li, G. (2021). Coordinating flexible demand response and renewable uncertainties for scheduling of community integrated energy systems with an electric vehicle charging station: A bi-level approach. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 12, 2321–2331.
- [25] Liu, S., Lin, Q., Li, J., & Tan, K. C. (2023). A survey on learnable evolutionary algorithms for scalable multiobjective optimization. *IEEE Transactions on Evolutionary Computation*, 27, 1941–1961. doi:[10.1109/TEVC.2023.1234567](https://doi.org/10.1109/TEVC.2023.1234567).
- [26] Luo, X., Shi, W., Jiang, Y., Liu, Y., & Xia, J. (2022). Distributed peer-to-peer energy trading based on game theory in a community microgrid considering ownership complexity of distributed energy resources. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 351, 131573.
- [27] Maldonado, J. L., Tostado-Véliz, M., Hasanien, H. M., Khosravi, N., & Jurado, F. (2024). Optimal planning of collective photovoltaic arrays in energy communities through a multi-cut benders' decomposition strategy. *Sustainable Cities and Society*, 104, 105307. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2210670724001355>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scs.2024.105307>.
- [28] Mishra, M., Singh, A., Misra, R. K., & Singh, D. (2022). Stochastic peer-to-peer energy trading with price and incentive mechanism. In *2022 22nd National Power Systems Conference (NPSC)* (pp. 761–766). doi:[10.1109/NPSC57038.2022.10069095](https://doi.org/10.1109/NPSC57038.2022.10069095).
- [29] Paredes, A., Aguado, J. A., & Rodriguez, P. (2023). Uncertainty-aware trading of congestion and imbalance mitigation services for multi-dso local flexibility markets. *IEEE Transactions on Sustainable Energy*, 14, 2133–2146.
- [30] Rahmaniani, R., Ahmed, S., Crainic, T. G., Gendreau, M., & Rei, W. (2020). The benders dual decomposition method. *Operations Research*, 68, 878–895.
- [31] Saavedra, R., Street, A., & Arroyo, J. M. (2020). Day-ahead contingency-constrained unit commitment with co-optimized post-contingency transmission switching. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 35, 4408–4420.
- [32] Sun, K., & Sun, X. A. (2021). A two-level admm algorithm for ac opf with global convergence guarantees. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, 36, 5271–5281.

- [33] Tönissen, D. D., Arts, J. J., & Shen, Z. J. M. (2021). A column-and-constraint generation algorithm for two-stage stochastic programming problems. *Top*, *29*, 781–798.
- [34] Wu, C., Chen, X., Hua, H., Yu, K., Gan, L., Shen, J., & Ding, Y. (2024). Peer-to-peer energy trading optimization for community prosumers considering carbon cap-and-trade. *Applied Energy*, *358*, 122611.
- [35] Xia, Y., Xu, Q., Tao, S., Du, P., Ding, Y., & Fang, J. (2022). Preserving operation privacy of peer-to-peer energy transaction based on enhanced benders decomposition considering uncertainty of renewable energy generations. *Energy*, *250*, 123567. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360544222004704>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2022.123567>.
- [36] Zeng, B., & Zhao, L. (2013). Solving two-stage robust optimization problems using a column-and-constraint generation method. *Operations Research Letters*, *41*, 457–461.
- [37] Zhang, B., Li, Q., Wang, L., & Feng, W. (2018). Robust optimization for energy transactions in multi-microgrids under uncertainty. *Applied Energy*, *217*, 346–360.
- [38] Zhang, H., Zhan, S., Kok, K., & Paterakis, N. G. (2024). Establishing a hierarchical local market structure using multi-cut benders decomposition. *Applied Energy*, *363*, 123073. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306261924004562>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123073>.
- [39] Zhang, Y., Li, T., & Wang, C. (2020). Distributed optimization for real-time distributed energy resources management using admm. *IEEE Transactions on Smart Grid*, *11*, 1124–1135.
- [40] Zhu, Y., Xiao, Y., Wang, X., Chen, C., Lu, Z., & Wang, X. (2024). Enhancing distribution system resilience with peer-to-peer transactions. *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, .